

VARIATION OF RESIDUAL THERMAL STRESSES IN GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The cure cycle of thermoset composites can cause residual stresses and strains in laminated structure due to the directional characteristics of the materials. Accurate analysis of residual stresses is critical for prediction of laminate strength. A three-dimensional finite element analysis is utilized in this study to obtain a detailed residual thermal stress/strain field. Applicability of the classical lamination theory and edge effects are discussed. In the area of a laminate more than six ply thicknesses away from the edge, three-dimensional analysis and classical lamination theory provide comparable results.

Keywords: Edge Effect; Finite Element Analysis; Residual Stress; Thermal Stress; Three-Dimensional.

INTRODUCTION

In the future, aerospace structures will be "smart structures". Such structures will have a network of embedded sensors and actuators. For example, laminated composite plates with embedded piezoceramics are proposed as smart skins for aircraft wings. Typically, piezoceramics have an allowable strain to failure that is one tenth that of most graphite/epoxy composites. Residual thermal stresses and strains gain importance in designing such composite laminates. This paper examines the residual thermal stress/strain field in a finite dimensional laminated plates.

Raghava^[1] demonstrated a variation of strain through the thickness of a thick laminated composite. Fulong^[2] experimentally investigated the Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) of a composite cube, including edge effects. These studies show a variation in the planar strain with changes in the location through the thickness. Barth^[3], Tsia^[4] and Tauchert^[5] have utilized closed form solutions for various cases of thermally induced strain in laminates. The thermal stress in a short fiber composite was investigated by Hatta^[6].

Bowles [7] used a two-dimensional finite element method to investigate CTE in laminates. The effect of element density in finite element modelling of thermally stressed laminates was evaluated by Crose [8].

In this paper, the results obtained using classical lamination theory are compared to the results obtained using three-dimensional (3-D) analysis to investigate the applicability of the classical lamination theory to residual thermal stress problems. The edge effects which can only be analyzed using three-dimensional analysis are also discussed

Table 1 Mechanical Properties of Materials Used.

Material property	Graphite/Epoxy
E ₁₁ GPa	132.7
E ₂₂ GPa	12.4
E ₃₃ GPa	12.4
G ₁₂ GPa	5.8
G ₁₃ GPa	5.8
G ₂₃ GPa	5.8
ν_{12}	0.30
ν_{13}	0.30
ν_{23}	0.30
α_1 mm/mm ^o K	-0.45×10^{-6}
α_2 mm/mm ^o K	27.5×10^{-6}
α_3 mm/mm ^o K	27.5×10^{-6}
t mm	0.254

ANALYSIS

A group of simple laminates are selected for the purpose of comparison. These laminates are [0₄/90₄]_S, [0₂/90₂]_{2S} and [0/90]_{4S}. The loads on the laminates are applied by assuming that the laminate's stress-free temperature was 154° C and measuring the laminate's strains at 24° C. This temperature history is compatible with the cure cycle that the materials in this study require. Table 1 lists the mechanical and thermal properties of the graphite/epoxy composite considered in this study.

Classical lamination theory assumes a continuous planar shell with small bending displacements. For a balanced and symmetric laminate, with no applied bending stresses, these assumptions produce a constant planar strain throughout the thickness of the laminate. This constant strain is then used to calculate the stress in each lamina. Classical lamination theory produced no differences in the strain distribution for the three laminates studied. These results are due to each of the laminates having the same percentage of 0° and 90° plies. These analyses also showed a midplane strain of -3.2449×10^{-4} mm/mm in both the X and Y directions for all of the laminates.

The three-dimensional analysis in this study is conducted using the ABAQUS version 4.8 finite element analysis code by Hibbitt, Karlsson & Sorensen, Inc. The laminates are modelled

as shown in Figure 1. The ABAQUS C3D8 element was used for this analysis. This is an eight-node linear displacement three-dimensional brick element. In order to obtain an accurate representation of the stress and strain variation through the thickness of each ply, each material orientation is modelled with at least two elements in the thickness direction. This is done so that stress and strain variations through the thickness of the laminate could be accurately represented.

Figure 1 Typical Three-Dimensional Model Used for Finite Element Analysis.

In order to ascertain that the finite element analysis provides convergent results and also to assure that the thermal stress/strain field is stabilized with respect to planar coordinates in the middle part of the laminates, the effect of several model variables is evaluated.

The first variable is the model's physical size. The comparison is accomplished by changing the X and Y dimension of the model without changing the number of elements or the dimension in the thickness direction. As the physical size of the model increased beyond 12.7 mm, the X direction strain becomes almost constant through the thickness. The next model variable investigated was the aspect ratio of the elements. For aspect ratios up to four, the results showed no change. An aspect ratio of six showed a small variation in X direction strain. As a final verification of the effect of physical size on the measured X direction strain, models of the same physical size were represented three different ways. A laminate modelled using four elements in the thickness direction is referred to as the four-element model. Another model with eight elements in the thickness direction is referred to as the eight-element model. The third model, referred to as the quarter model, has the X-Y, X-Z and Y-Z planes all defined as planes of symmetry. For the first two models only the X-Y plane was a plane of symmetry, with the corner nodes falling on the X or Y axis restrained to only move along the axis. For the four-element and eight-element models, the physical size was the actual model dimensions in the X or Y directions. For the quarter model, the model dimension was half that of the physical model size.

As a result of the model variable study, it was concluded that the most accurate model size was a 50.8-mm model. At this physical size there was no apparent variation in X direction strain through the thickness of the model. To achieve this model dimension and minimize the effect of element aspect ratio, a quarter model is selected. It should be noted that, the X-Z and Y-Z planes of symmetry can only be used if the laminate being modelled contains only 0° and 90° plies.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The stacking sequence comparison for [0₄/90₄]_s, [0₂/90₂]_{2s} and [0,90]_{4s} laminates was run using the 50.8-mm quarter model that resulted from the model variable study. Figure 2 shows the results of the comparison. There was no variation in X direction strain through the thickness of the laminates. However, there was a slight difference in the value of the strain obtained using three-dimensional analysis and classical lamination theory.

Figure 2 Stacking Sequence Comparison for a Model Size of 50.8 mm.

The lack of variation of strain through the thickness of the laminate can be verified using the following analysis:

Consider a laminated orthotropic plate whose thickness is very small compared to its planar dimensions. Let us assume that strain components are not a function of the planar coordinates sufficiently far away from the edges of the plate, that is ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} , ϵ_{zz} , ϵ_{xz} , ϵ_{yz} , ϵ_{xy} strains are a function of Z coordinate only. Using linear elastic constitutive relations, we obtain σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} , σ_{zz} , σ_{xz} , σ_{yz} , σ_{xy} stresses are a function of Z only.

Substituting stress components in equilibrium equations yields:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{xz}}{\partial z} = 0; \frac{\partial \sigma_{yz}}{\partial z} = 0; \frac{\partial \sigma_{zz}}{\partial z} = 0$$

Which implies, $\sigma_{xz} = \text{constant}$, $\sigma_{yz} = \text{constant}$, $\sigma_{zz} = \text{constant}$.

Assuming lateral plate surfaces are traction free (no mechanical loading) implies:

$$\sigma_{xz}=0 \quad \sigma_{yz}=0 \quad \sigma_{zz}=0$$

Substituting in constitutive relations, yields,

$$\epsilon_{xz}=0, \epsilon_{yz}=0$$

$$\text{and, } C_{13}\epsilon_{xx}+C_{23}\epsilon_{yy}+C_{33}\epsilon_{zz}=0$$

which implies

$$\epsilon_{xx}=\text{constant}$$

$$\epsilon_{yy}=\text{constant}$$

$$\epsilon_{zz}=\text{constant}$$

This shows that the initial assumption is not true. Normal strains are constant and shear strains are identically zero throughout the thickness of the plate sufficiently away from the edges (where strains are no more functions of planar coordinates).

EDGE EFFECTS

Edge effects will be discussed for $[0_4/90_4]_S$, $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ and $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminates in this section. These laminates were modelled using the quarter model geometry. For the $[0_4/90_4]_S$ and $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ laminates, 25 elements were used in the X and Y directions and eight elements were used in the Z direction. For the $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate, 20 elements were used in the X and Y directions and 16 elements were used in the Z direction. All models had physical dimensions of 4.06 X 50.8 X 50.8 mm.

The variation of X direction strain as distance from the edge increases is as shown in Figure 3. The strain shown in this figure was for the nodes that lie on the X axis of a quarter model. This represents the midplane strain in the center of the model. The midplane strain was shown for three different laminates, $[0_4/90_4]_S$, $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ and $[0/90]_{4S}$, with the results of classical lamination theory shown for comparison.

Figure 3 X Direction Strain at the Midplane of the Model.

All three three-dimensional models converge to the results of classical lamination theory at a distance of 8.89 mm from the edge of the model. The magnitude of the strain at the free

edge appears to vary in a linear manner with respect to the number of plies of the same orientation that are located adjacent to one another. The rate of convergence to the classical lamination theory results varies in the same manner.

The variation of interlaminar normal stress was also investigated. The interlaminar stress is plotted for the nodes that lie on the first 90°/0° material interface away from the midplane of the lamina. For the [0₄/90₄]_s case, this was the fifth node from the midplane. For the [0₂/90₂]_{2s} and [0/90]_{4s} laminates, this was the third node from the center. Figure 4 shows the interlaminar normal stress for the cases studied. Once again the edge effect diminishes within 8.89 mm from the edge of the model. A high compressive stress can be seen at the edge of the laminate. This stress was reacted by a tensile stress 2.03 to 8.89 mm from the edge of the model. The magnitude of the stress varies in proportion to the number of adjacent similar plies.

Figure 4 Z Direction Stress at the First 0°/90° Interface Away From the Laminate Midplane.

In Figure 5 the X-Z shear stress was reported at the same interface as the interlaminar normal stress. The shear stress shows the same response reported by Fulong[2]. The shear stress approaches zero within four to six lamina thicknesses of the edge of the laminate.

Figure 5 X-Z Shear Stress at the First 0°/90° Interface Away From the Laminate Midplane.

The variation of X direction strain through the thickness of the laminate at the free edge is shown in Figure 6. The strain at the midplane was equivalent to the strain of a lamina twice the thickness of the rest of the lamina, due to the midplane symmetry condition used. It can be seen that the midplane strain of the $[0_4/90_4]_S$ laminate is the same as the strain of the $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ laminate at the fifth node from the centerline. Both of these two lamina have two plies of 90° material at these locations.

It can also be seen that at the surface of the models the strains tend toward the strain of an unrestrained 0° lamina. However, the fewer the number of plies in a lamina, the closer to the classical approximation were its free surface strains.

The edge effects seen in the $[90/0]_S$ class of laminates was similar to the edge effects seen in the $[0/90]_S$ class. The X direction data for the $[90/0]_S$ class is identical to Y direction data for the $[0/90]_S$ class of laminate. The edge distance influenced was almost identical. The stresses and strains change sign as would be expected when the stacking sequence is reversed. The magnitude of the stresses changes due to the stiffness of the 0° and 90° material.

Figure 6 X Direction Strains Through the Thickness of the Laminates at the Free Edge.

The free edge X direction strain for $[90/0]_S$ class laminates is shown in Figure 7. At the surface the strains tend to the strain of an unrestrained 90° lamina. The magnitude of the strain shows a linear response at the free surface for the one-ply and two-ply layers. The magnitude of the strain of the four-ply layer is not twice that of the two-ply layer due to its proximity to the magnitude of an unrestrained lamina.

The X direction strain at the midplane is shown in Figure 8 for the $[90/0]_S$ class of laminate which shows similar behavior to the $[0/90]_S$ class. In both cases the strains converge to the value predicted by classical lamination theory within 8.89 mm of the free edge. However, the magnitude of the free edge strain is smaller when compared to the $[0/90]_S$ laminates. This is caused by the smaller CTE and greater modulus of the 0° material.

Figure 7 X Direction Strains Through the Thickness of the Laminates at the Free edge.

The interlaminar normal stresses at the $90^\circ/0^\circ$ interface is shown in Figure 9. A tensile stress can be seen at the free edge of the laminate. This was consistent with the contraction of the 90° plies on the surface of the laminate and the expansion of the 0° plies at the midplane of the laminate. The stress at the edge was reacted by a compressive stress away from the edge of the laminate.

Figure 8 X Direction Strain at the Midplane of the Model.

Figure 9 Z Direction Stress at the First $90^\circ/0^\circ$ Interface Away From the Laminate Midplane.

The X-Z shear stress edge effect, as shown in Figure 10, for the $[90/0]_S$ laminates demonstrates the same trends as the shear stress of the $[0/90]_S$ laminates. In both cases the stress diminishes within six lamina thicknesses from the edge of the laminate.

Figure 10 X-Z Shear Stress at the First $90^\circ/0^\circ$ Interface Away From the Laminate Midplane.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that for large laminates the in-plane strains do not vary with respect to the thickness location when observed sufficiently away from the edges of the laminate. For these cases, classical lamination theory predicts an accurate residual thermal stress/strain field inside laminates.

The three-dimensional analysis has shown that for the laminates studied, the magnitude of the in-plane strains measured at a free edge are proportional to the total thickness of adjacent material with like orientation. Also the in-plane strains converge to the value predicted by classical lamination theory in less than six times the maximum thickness of a single orientation of material. The magnitude of the normal interlaminar stress was also proportional to the maximum total thickness of adjacent material with like orientation. The analysis also showed that an opening stress at a free edge was reacted by a compressive stress further away from the edge.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Raghava, R. S., Valentich, J., and Nathenson, R. D., "Thermoelastic Behavior of Thick Glass/Epoxy Composite Laminates", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 18, Jan. 1984, pp. 81-93.

- [2] Fulong, D., Yinyan, W., and Post, D. "Residual Thermal Strains in a Laminated Composite", *Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Composite Materials*, Vol 2, 1989, pp. 177-180.
- [3] Barth, T. S., Joshi, S. P., and Pearlstein, A. J., "Three-Dimensional Thermoelasticity Formulation For Laminated Transversely Isotropic Solids", *Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Composite Materials*, Vol 2, 1989, pp. 192-197.
- [4] Tsia, Y. M., "Orthotropic Thermoelastic Problem of Uniform Heat Flow Disturbed By a Central Crack," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 18, March 1984, pp. 122-131.
- [5] Tauchert, T. R., "Thermal Shock of Symmetric Cross-Ply Laminates," *Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Composite Materials*, Vol 2, 1989, pp. 165-170.
- [6] Hatta, H. and Taya, M., "Thermal Stress in a Coated Short Fiber Composite," *Transactions of the ASME Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology*, Vol. 109 no. 1, Jan. 1987, pp. 59-63.
- [7] Bowles, D. E., "Effect of Microcracks on the Thermal Expansion of Composite Laminates," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 17, March. 1984, pp. 173-187.
- [8] Crose, J. G., Holman, R. L., and Pagano, N. J. "Validation of Advanced Composite Thermal Stress Analysis Methods," *Transactions of the ASME Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology*, Vol. 109 no. 1, Jan. 1987, pp. 40-46.